

THE ROLE OF TEACHING ENGLISH AND THE SIGNIFICANCE OF COMMUNICATION SKILLS TO THE MECHANICAL ENGINEERING STUDENTS

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Abstract The article supplies us with the data about the necessity and significance of teaching English to Mechanical Engineering students and the role of English and an importance of communication skills. It is true that Engineering is one of the vital fields of study in the world and many research works and studies results are published in English. English is very important for non-native English speakers because it is widely spoken all over the world. Influential English gives a chance people to enjoy their life and work without problems where they are. For Mechanical Engineering students whose mother tongue is not English, mastering English is even more vital, not only for their academic life but also for their future career. So the present article will highlight the significance of English and how English can reduce the employability by learning communication skills. It also assists the people to get a daydream job through communication skills. It also looks at the different ways of learning communication skills through communicative activities.

Keywords: English Language Teaching, Communication skills, Lingua Franca, Mechanical Engineering.

Аннотация В статье представлены данные о необходимости и значении преподавания английского языка студентам-механикам, а также о роли английского языка и важности коммуникативных навыков. Это правда, что инженерное дело является одной из важнейших областей обучения в мире, и многие исследовательские работы и результаты исследований публикуются на английском языке. Английский очень важен для тех, для кого английский язык не является родным, поскольку на нем широко говорят

во всем мире. Влиятельный английский дает людям возможность без проблем наслаждаться жизнью и работать там, где они находятся. Для студентов-механиков, чей родной язык не английский, овладение английским языком еще более важно не только для их академической жизни, но и для их будущей карьеры. Таким образом, в настоящей статье будет подчеркнута важность английского языка и то, как английский может снизить возможности трудоустройства за счет изучения навыков общения. Это также помогает людям получить работу мечты благодаря коммуникативным навыкам. Также рассматриваются различные способы обучения коммуникативным навыкам посредством коммуникативной деятельности.

Ключевые слова: преподавание английского языка, коммуникативные навыки, Lingua Franca, машиностроение.

Annotatsiya Maqolada mashinasozlik fakulteti talabalariga ingliz tilini o'rgatishning zarurligi va ahamiyati, ingliz tilining o'rni va muloqot ko'nikmalarining ahamiyati haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan. To'g'ri, muhandislik dunyoda o'rganishning muhim yo'nalishlaridan biri bo'lib, ko'plab tadqiqot ishlari va tadqiqot natijalari ingliz tilida nashr etiladi. Ingliz tili ona tili bo'lmagan inglizlar uchun juda muhim, chunki u butun dunyoda keng tarqalgan. Nufuzli ingliz tili odamlarga o'z hayotlaridan zavqlanish va ular turgan joyda muammosiz ishlash imkoniyatini beradi. Ona tili ingliz tili bo'lmagan Mashina muhandisligi talabarlari uchun ingliz tilini o'zlashtirish nafaqat ularning akademik hayoti, balki kelajakdagi faoliyati uchun ham muhimroqdir. Shunday qilib, ushbu maqola ingliz tilining ahamiyatini va ingliz tili muloqot qobiliyatlarini o'rganish orqali ishga joylashishni qanday kamaytirishi mumkinligini ta'kidlaydi. Bu, shuningdek, muloqot qobiliyatlari orqali odamlarga orzu qilingan ish topishga yordam beradi. Shuningdek, u kommunikativ faoliyat orqali muloqot qobiliyatlarini o'rganishning turli usullarini ko'rib chiqadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Ingliz tilini o'qitish, muloqot qobiliyatlari, Lingua Franca, mashinasozlik.

Introduction English language is the most significant function of students being performed in their life social life. English language provide to build strong relationship and better understanding which are so vital in their personal and professional life. To be victorious in any field one need to know and understand how to communicate effectively. In the era of LPG (Liberalization, Privatization and Globalization), good communication expertise are the keys to unlock the doors of success. As we all know it is an international language along with this it is an official language in the world. It is a primary language of global trade & commerce used in international affairs. We are living in the digital age where we have to make the software's, deal with various technologies & Internet. All over the world the language which is used is only English. So English is the language of latest version applications and programs and new era where, shoreward, peer to peer, social media networks and all websites, all the software instruction booklets, installation guides and product fact sheets of populate consumer electronics and entertainment devices usually are available in English first before having made available in other languages. Speaking English fluently is an important criterion of the admission process and a candidate's ability to master this ability brightens their chances of admissions to foreign Universities. In National University of Singapore, students are required to pass Qualifying English Test to assess their proficiency of English language. To a certain level where students are not able to qualify, there is inevitability for them to go for extra English module to brush up their English. Such measurements are carried out to make sure the students are able to write, listen, and communicate with proficient English in future. At present in India there are thousands of Mechanical Engineering students are facing employment crises. There are many reasons behind it. First and foremost reason is lack of

communication and unable to handle the English language. This paper deals how to empower language and communication through some suggestions.

English as an academic language As far as English Language Teaching is concerned, before coming down to actual curriculums, it is of utmost importance to determine the position of English as an academic language and its role in the studies of mechanical engineering. It is obvious that today English is not learned only for the pleasure and prestige of knowing a foreign language, but also because of the fact that it has become the language of international currents in technology and commerce. The knowledge of any language used to be a sign of a well-rounded education, but with no clear reason as to why it was necessary. However, as English became the accepted lingua franca of modern technology and commerce, a number of learners with specific reasons for learning English came to the front: business people who wanted to sell their products, doctors and engineers who needed to stay in touch with the new developments in their respective fields, and most importantly for us, students who needed to use textbooks and journals available only in English, and who needed English in order to advance and succeed in their careers. That is how many different reasons for studying English sprang out all of a sudden. (Hutchinson and Waters, 2000)

Language and communication The need for learning a language arises from the point of view of its adaptability, productivity, utility, universality and teachability. Communication is a sharing of feelings, ideas and opinions with others. This can be intellectual, personnel spoken or written in nature. We live in groups and man is invariably a social animal. As the social needs insist, we share our thoughts with others. The two-way processes of communication motivates, inform, suggests, warns, orders, changing behaviour and establiity better relationships to make interaction meaningful and make oneself understood.

English for specific and academic purposes Thus, if we take into consideration the generally accepted purposes for which the English language is

needed and learned and the necessity of the basic language skills required (listening, speaking, reading and writing), we can divide its usage into those for general, specific and social purposes. English for General purposes, or as it is sometimes called "TENOR" ("the Teaching of English for No Obvious Reason"), is the type of English that usually young learners acquire and that is not specified by any identifiable need. English for Social Purposes, on the other hand, is mostly taught to adult learners and deals mainly with conversational purposes and communicative situations. Some of its aspects, such as letter-writing and the ability to operate functionally in an English speaking environment, are often a part of English for Academic Purposes (EAP) courses in English-speaking countries. The third type is English for Specific Purposes (ESP), that is, the type of the English Language Teaching which we are most interested in. (Jordan, 1997) Figure The Purposes for Learning English (Jordan, 1997:3) The Role of English and The Importance of Communication to The Mechanical Engineering Students <http://www.iaeme.com/IJMET/index.asp> 785 editor@iaeme.com The Role of English Language for Mechanical Engineering Communication Engineering is the biggest field of study in the world. First of all, English is a tool that notably affect Mechanical engineering students in academic life. While most of the assumptions in mechanical engineering are taught in English, it requires having good English communication proficiency. In academic life, mechanical engineering students have to deal with the countless lectures, tutorials, labs, project reports and papers in English. Generally mechanical engineering professors in various universities are also conducting lectures in English. The most apt source of information i.e. Internet provides generally the information in English. During the job seeking process in interviews, GD's, it is it is mandatory to achieve mastery in English proficiency. After securing the job they are necessary to work in groups since their task seldom be solved by an individual. A Large number of Indian mechanical engineers have to now travel to many continents and work away from their

domicile country. Also, among the scientists, technologists and business experts from culturally and linguistically different communities, English has become the prime language for communication. So, being a mechanical engineer requires co-operating and communicating with different people from different part of the world. English is used as the operational language on large extent. In order to harmonize with the colleagues, engineers have to speak fluent English. So, English communication competence plays an important role in the academic life and career of mechanical engineering students. ELT and the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering English Language Teaching for the students of mechanical engineering tries to highlight the most necessary and adequate language skills they might require. The most crucial of all decisions is the one concerning the exact dosage of many ingredients needed for a successful language course. Just how much General English and ESAP get into the curriculum depends on many various conditions. As far as General English is concerned, it is important to know how many years prior to this course the students studied English. It is usually the case that the students are at many different levels, when it comes to the English language knowledge, and there are often situations where students are studying English for the first time, since they can choose the language they wish to study only at the university level. Therefore, it is necessary to cover all the basic grammar units and language skills before proceeding to English for Specific Academic Purposes. This will often include having to work with students primarily on their listening and reading skills, and slowly moving toward what is often much more difficult and frightening for them that is, speaking and writing. Raising the proficiency of language use, and sometimes even creating it, will, thus, lead to more specific aspects of the English language necessary for their academic studies and future careers. Going in this direction, from general to specific, will in the end lead ton what can easily be described as the aforementioned ESAP, which will here constitute of scientific terminology, basic mathematical, physical and chemical

principles and laws, and a majority of mechanical engineering aspects, ranging from fundamental mechanics to cutting-edge computer science. Effective Communication English language communication is the most common problem faced by students. Most students are not “industry ready” because they lack communication skills. There is no effective communication between the faculty-student and student-student. No effective training is imparted to the students who are very poor at communication. Much importance is being given to the technical skills ignoring the most indispensable communication skills. To perform effectively in the business world or organization, communication plays a pivotal role. One who is good at effective communication thinks soundly, enjoys self-esteem, dignity and gets respect in society, academic or profession. People frequently fail to communicate effectively because they don’t express themselves clearly or forcefully enough. Or, they may go to the other extreme, expressing themselves in such a belligerent way that they alienate others. Employability refers to a person’s capability of gaining initial employment maintaining employment, and obtaining new employment if required (Hillage and Pollare, 1998). It depends on knowledge, skills and attitude the employer seeks. In order to be employable it is important to understand the needs of the market place and identify what skills you already have and what skills you need to include in your career plan. In a list of skills and attributes identified by companies that belong to National Association of Career Educators and Employment (NACE) communication skills holds the first position. It’s mandatory to have effective English invariable of the sector and industry. Professional needs to assess and respond to communication situations that occur constantly. The four main goals of communication are • To inform • To request • To persuade and • To build relationships with others. In today’s India without English, a student cannot enter the sophisticated world of science and technology. Further, in the present global context, it is felt that English is of paramount importance. Certain Suggestions on Communication for The

mechanical Engineering students Be a team player. Professional engineering involves collaboration among many different disciplines that must come together to resolve complex issues and formulate solutions to bring products to market. As a result, communication skills are as important as technical expertise Be part of the innovation pipeline. Always be open to new ideas, even if they come from sources outside your group. Beware of the Not-Invented-Here bias that exists at some companies. Companies will reward engineers who encourage innovative ideas, regardless of where they originated. Keep learning. This is crucial as the tools used to do product design and analysis are constantly changing and improving. Stay ahead of the curve and seek out new assignments and opportunities to learn new technologies, sign up for training programs and make the most of company-paid educational benefits. Beef up your communication skills Many Mechanical Engineers prefer to stick to the technical design track, while others will want to branch off into management roles, which means you'll need to be comfortable talking to customers, giving presentations and working with outside suppliers, agencies, etc. Developing these "soft" skills is vital for engineers who aspire to be managers one day. Toastmasters International, a non-profit organization, is a great place to get your feet wet in public speaking English empowers young minds not only in passing exams but in demonstrating their acumen before the world. Technical institutions have realized the importance of communicating in English in response to the increasing needs of job market. Most of the organizations require people in different capacities with good communication abilities which comprise interacting with customers and clients, explaining policies and procedures, entertaining foreign clients, conducting meeting, delivering presentations, liaising, responding to customer complaints and taking orders, etc. Since the world has gone global, the need to compete in it without efficiency in English is difficult. Many organizations have started training their employees in English from time to time. This has ameliorated the life styles of people who considered their future

blocked forever if they failed to make it to teaching or some other traditional jobs. In fact, the knowledge of English plays a role in all times

Conclusion The teacher is the realistic communicative motivator, who designs appropriate tasks for the students to express genuine information. To encourage the students to use English to communicate with the other students, the students' motivation and interest in the process of group working for English Learning task could be stimulated much greater. The preparing activities such as brainstorming and pre-task planning are also used so that the students could create some new ideas on what to say and some expressions and suggestions on how to express their ideas and creativities, to express their ideas and creative. Thus today, it can be said that though English has almost lost its pre-colonial beauty of literariness, but it has acquired a very colourful communicative mode. Just like the fast moving consumer goods, English language is transforming its multidimensional communicative structure day by day, and in the process has enhanced its utility quotient in India. English is available to us as a historical heritage in addition to our own language. We must make the best use of it to develop ourselves culturally and materially so that we can compete with the best in world of mind and matters. Good and effective Communication makes the Mechanical Engineering students as world brand and eradicates the unemployment.

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